

Research Writing Aid for Non- English-Speaking Research Novices

Abstract

Non-English speakers continue to encounter challenges in writing a scholarly research paper. This problem continues to linger on. This study employs a qualitative research approach in using works of literature to address mistakes that novice in academic research face. The study is conducted from the perspective of Non-English speakers' problems they encounter. The study suggests Important elements needed in writing scholarly research papers. This study is of novel effects for non-English speakers and novice researchers.

Keywords: Non-English speakers, research writing, Novice, Researcher

Introduction

Tertiary education continues to be a vital element for training students in acquiring advanced, critical, analytics, and systematics skills that are needed in solving world, societal, work, personal, and many more related issues. It has also been a growing avenue in helping to eliminate literacy in the world (Ortiz-Ospina, 2018; UNESCO, 2017). Academic research has been a requirement for university students in different language settings. Some students continue to find it challenging to conduct academic research, most especially students who have not had any research writing background (Walden University, 2010). Professors, lecturers, researchers, etc. have published and taught many lessons on how to write academic research (Creswell, Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches, 2017; Cathy J. Thompson, 2014; Baffoe, 2017; Al Fadda, 2012; Yang C. , 2017; Yang X. &. , 2016; Wilkinson, 1991; Sterling, 2017; Ravitch, 2012). Whereas native English speakers are challenged with the difficulty of writing academic research papers, non-native English-speaker who are novices to writing an academic research paper equally go through many hurdles than them (Al Fadda, 2012). Notable researchers have written papers to help non-English speakers on what to do to improve their academic writing skills (Yang C. , 2017; Srikrai, 2016; Yang X. &. , 2016). Researchers such as Al Fadda (2012) identified that grammar in academic writing is a challenge for non-English speakers, Yang (2016) researched on grammar and accent challenges that have effects on academic writing for non-English speakers, Yang (2017) also used her practical experience as a Chinese foreign student to highlight the trials non-native English speakers face with English proficiency and the knowledge of academic writing. Several researchers have addressed the pitfalls non-English speakers face with academic writing; nonetheless conceptual framework, ethics of research writing, research

writing style and many others have not been addressed from the perspective of Non-English speakers, and this study hopes to fill this gap.

The purpose of this study is to explain and outline in simple detail ways deducing from works of literature and personal experiences of how a novice researcher from a non-English speaking country could scale his or her way through the academic ladder with this informational help. This would better educate beginners to be well equipped with the life skills of conducting researches. High school, undergraduate and even master's students who are not familiar with research writing can take a key from this study.

The paper would be outlined as follow: Academic research and its importance. Research ethics and the role of the researcher, Conceptual framework, choosing a research topic, vital elements of an academic research paper, implication, conclusion, limitation and future research.

Academic Research and its Importance.

Critical thinking an essential part of education is encouraged in academic research writing. This aid researchers to utilize other researchers work as evidence to promote one's idea or contribute to the domain of literatures in a specific field (Carley, 1992; Jia Guo, 2013). According to Baffoe (2017), research can be attributed to a person who first listens to what others are communicating in a conversation setting before, he or she can join in the conversation with a contribution. In the discourse of academic knowledge, there is a need always to study and learn from previous researchers to gain a grounded foundation on what to work and develop on as a topic(s) in a particular field or as a discovery of new knowledge.

The influence of research has a strong effect on our daily life, from marketing, health, education, transportation, security, religion, etc. For example, the supply and demand of vaccines used to curb an epidemic can be identified when research is done to find out what the problem that brought about the plague is? How did it come about? When did the epidemic start? Where did it originate? Who or which species or people had the impact? What is the remedy to prevent this from happening again in the future? Real problems of this nature prompt researches to be conducted on a problem or issue. This research question probes one to dig further to find answers to problems that need to be solved. It is essential that in a University setting, a student should be abreast with writing academic research to develop one's critical thinking for addressing societal pressing issues that need to be looked at and solved. To be able to join the academic field of researchers, It is crucial to have a good foundation and knowledge in critical thinking that can be encouraged through academic research writing.

Research Ethics and the Role of the Researcher.

The worse thing in life is to lose Integrity and trust from people, and so does the academic world also work. Ethics which is a guide, rules or regulations created to ensure orderliness, trust and honesty in the way one conducted his or her research is a foundation block for academic work. Notable Institutional Academic Board or world bodies like the American Psychiatric Association (APA) and many others who set standards that aim at ensuring that one's work can be seen as genuine, authentic and accepted in the world of scholarly writing helps to train people on academic ethics in the research field (Sterling, 2017). Research ethics serve as guides for researchers on how data is collected,

analysed, presented, coupled with the format of the research writing style, plagiarism prevention, protecting intellectual property right that aims to encourage innovative ideas in one's research field helps to promote the continuity of a research field (Gabriel, 2010). To ensure that literature shared with the academic world of discussion, the enforcement of ethics is an essential element that a researcher needs to take note of and use. Many prominent people have been defamed, disgraced, or lost credibility as a result of not following ethical guidance in their professional field or work such as plagiarizing other people's work by not giving credit to their work. For example, musicians such as Mariah Carey, Black Eye Peas and the others have lost their credibility as a result of plagiarizing other people's song lyrics (Friedman, 2004). Students are dismissed from schools due to this act of academic dishonesty because the ethics in academic writing was not adhered to (Gabriel, 2010).

Scholarly research is achieved through the role of the researcher. To ensure that the academic study is peer-reviewed, formatted, ethically worked on to provide a good result for academic contribution to a field, the role the researcher plays is essential to the quality of the paper. It is important that researchers' study well the knowledge in their areas, the ethics, writing format to understand how their role is important in adding value to research works of literature that have already been conducted (Creswell, *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches*, 2017). Developments in a society, nation or company are achieved through researches, and the people that do that are the researchers, so young researchers must understand how vital research work is to humanity and the part they will play when they begin their research work.

Conceptual framework

The lens of this study is guided by a combination of dimensions that is used as a framework for this research (Creswell, Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches, 2017). The diagram below depicts the conceptual framework supporting this study.

Source: Conceptual framework, developed by the author

Choosing a research topic and methodology

The topic of interest motivates the methodology needed for research. Choosing a research consist of the ideas required by scaling through academic journals, papers, books, newspapers, issues surrounding us that needs attention or personal experiences

that one wants to probe into to find more answers (Creswell, Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches, 2017). Furthermore, after reviewing many materials, it is essential to focus on a specific topic of interest and its keywords for further reading. Creswell (2017), gives more details on choosing a research topic.

Also, whiles the research topic keywords are gotten there is a need to state the research background, problem and questions that the paper aims at solving or address. For more information about choosing a research topic, please refer to (Creswell, Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches, 2017; Walden University, 2010). Without a clear picture of what your research is all about, the problem and questions that called for the study, it would be challenging to know which methodology to use in solving the research problem. Research methodology approaches such as qualitative, quantitative and mixed-method are the known academic research approach used for academic writing (Creswell, Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches, 2017). Using qualitative research approach keywords notably used are “explore, explain, and many more”. Whiles in quantitative research approach words that are also used are words such as “correlation, relationship, and many more”. Though the two-research approach is suitable for academic research, the mixed method research approach is seen as a very rigour approach to researching a problem as it combines both qualitative and quantitative research approach (Creswell, Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches, 2017). Researchers are advised to learn the rules of these research approaches. They are also cautioned to learn how to employ mixed method approach as it is a method that is time-consuming and its ethics need to be followed (Baffoe, 2017; Creswell, Research design: Qualitative,

quantitative, and mixed methods approaches, 2017). The skills, knowledge, rules and ethics of how to choose a research topic and methodology opens the door of the academic world to a researcher.

Key Element of academic research

OUTLINE OF AN ABSTRACT

An executive summary that is written for an official report in the working settings, the abstract also serves as a concise summary of the research that is conducted. The Abstract which serves as a snapshot of what the fundamental research is about contains structured elements in academia. In the abstract it should have the brief background of the issue or problem that led to the research, the purpose of the study, mostly the word “purpose” is used to indicate the central ideal used and followed by the data that would be used and its collection methods if there are human participants in qualitative approach the ethical procedures that were used. Statistical results are then outlined, and the abstract is concluded with the practical implication of the research of the study (Creswell, Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches, 2017). Usually, the abstract should not have more than 250 words (Creswell, Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches, 2013). Properly writing an abstract encourages readers to take an interest in reading the full paper of a researcher from first glance.

INTRODUCTION

Readers are given a transparent background with supporting referencing in the introduction. Wilkinson (1991), noted that the introduction’s “purpose is to establish a

framework for the research so that readers can understand how it related to other research”. According to Creswell (2013), an introduction should have the following elements:

1. Research problem need to be stated,
2. Studies that have addressed the problem of research need to be reviewed and referred to,
3. Research gaps found in the reviewed studies on the problem need to be indicated,
4. The significance of the study needs to be indicated to specify the stakeholders and audiences the study hope to benefit,
5. The purpose of the research needs to be specified, as well as the outline of the study need to be included.

Amidst all the above, non-native speakers faces the challenge on how to write a good research introduction paragraph. In writing a section in the research paper, there is a need for a novice to learn more about what a “hook statement”, “thesis statement”, and “Meal plan” are to enrich the construction of their introduction (Duke University Thompson Writing Program, n.d.). These elements help one to structure an academic paragraph into a scholarly cognitive way to have the study ideas connected with precision.

LITERATURE REVIEW (RESEARCH CONTRIBUTION FROM THE AUTHOR USUALLY IS MISSING)

The foundation of any research work is the literature review. A literature review is a requisite for writing a scholarly paper. From the experiences had in China, non-English speakers and English speakers do not know that using literature review only does not give your essay a strong backing without adding your contribution to the literatures reviewed to support the study. (Creswell, Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and

mixed methods approaches, 2013). It is crucial for novice researcher especially non-English speakers to take keen interest adding their contribution they hope to add to all the literatures they have reviewed to add their voice in the discourse of literature presented.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK/ CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Gaining the clarity of ideas of an article gives a logical inference of what the topic of the study is about and how it would be conducted. Theoretical framework or conceptual framework used in integrating concepts, a phenomenon or world views of ideas is used in organizing the structure of the research in a logical, concise manner for readers to understand (Cathy J. Thompson, 2014; Ravitch, 2012). According to Cathy (2014), a theoretical framework is a conceptual abstract of phenomena used as a framework to guide research. Though it is an acceptable means to structure a study for readers to find the correlation between the logic and information of the study conducted, the drawbacks of theoretical framework are that the theory is adopted from a phenomenon used as a fixed framework for a study which does not give room for different concepts to be integrated to study a problem (Ravitch, 2012; Dressman, 2008). A theoretical framework is useful for many studies; nonetheless, not all studies that need that (Ravitch, 2012; Dressman, 2008). To address this gap, the research's propounded conceptual framework as another tool used as a guide for researchers to fuse different concepts, phenomena within or outside a field that are related to the study to guide the research (Ravitch, 2012). Ravitch (2012), in their book on ***Reason and rigour, how conceptual frameworks to guide to research***, stressed on the importance of researchers using a conceptual framework to prevent one from being limited to an already adopted theory for a research whiles different

concepts of a phenomenon could be used together to address the dynamism of a study. Academic research is seen as scholarly when a fusion of a theoretical or conceptual framework is included.

RESULT FINDINGS, DISCUSSION, CONCLUSION, IMPLICATIONS, LIMITATIONS, AND FUTURE RESEARCH

The importance and crowning of a research study give the reader a vivid picture of the researcher's contribution, weakness and proposed study for the future. The brainwork of any research is the description, analyses, interpretation of data to get the findings of the results from the questions asked which is addressed in the implications (George Mason University, n.d.; MacLean, 1999). The research implication contains the credibility of one's research which lies in the reliability, validity and how the data was used in addressing the research questions under study. Results of what the data reflects serve as a relation to the research question used in ascertaining the usefulness of its implication to stakeholders (for example, academicians, policy makers, industries, etc.). Novice researcher or non-English speakers should take keen interest in investing time and efforts in preparing their research implication well as it carries the whole meaning and importance of the research under study.

More so, the conclusion of research reaffirms, and outlines points from the research question used and how the results of the findings from the question posed have been addressed or not. More so, it also looks at or gives a recommendation for future research studies (George Mason University, n.d.).

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study used literature as a source of review to address and outline concerns that non-English speakers face when writing an academic research paper. Though the study did not focus on all the outline of a research paper, it focused on the salient areas that most non-speakers like Chinese students face when writing an academic essay. This research was motivated by personal experiences with non-English speakers as well as English speakers. Though this research addresses gaps that were not looked at in other studies, future researchers could do further research by using qualitative research approaches such as interview, focus group discussion, survey to get a real sense of what students from non-English speaking countries face and how best this can be curtailed from different countries' education systems most especially from the University settings. This research calls for more review of educational curriculums and teaching skills to help fill up the gap.

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